

The logo for INSTINCT features the word "INSTINCT" in a bold, white, sans-serif font. The letter "S" is replaced by a stylized, blue, 3D-rendered shape that resembles a double helix or a pair of interlocking curves. The background of the top section is dark blue with a network of white lines and dots, suggesting a digital or scientific theme.

INSTINCT

D5.2

Interim dissemination, communication and standardisation report

TID

The bottom half of the page features a dark blue background with a complex network of white lines and dots, similar to the top section but with a more prominent, glowing blue network structure in the center.

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PU Public, fully open. e.g., website ✓

SEN Confidential to INSTINCT project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R - Document, report

DMP – Data Management Plan

DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

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Executive Summary

This document represents the deliverable D5.2 with the report on the dissemination, communication and standardisation activities performed during the first half of the INSTINCT project.

INSTINCT is committed to maximize the impact and disseminate the results obtained during the course of the project. The dissemination strategy adopted during the inception of the project aimed at raising awareness of the project objectives and disseminating the obtained results and outcomes. The target audience was a technical community from the field of communication systems. In the dissemination activities, we listed a total of 51 journal publications, 25 conference publications, 3 book chapters and white papers and 30 talks and other related events, supporting the strong commitment of INSTINCT towards spreading the project results to a wide audience.

The communication efforts involve the promotion of the project outcomes beyond the communication systems community, using a methodology based on simple messages that lay people can read and understand. We measured incoming/outcoming traffic to the project website and the large values showed an existing interest in INSTINCT. In addition, the LinkedIn account is a huge success and is receiving a lot of attention. So far, we have gathered more than 470 subscriptions, more than 45000 impressions, and more than 800 reactions. Finally, up to 10 standardisation activities have been performed so far involving different standardisation bodies such as 3GPP and ETSI, among others.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Standardisation, Open source, Plans, Strategy, Tools

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this deliverable

This deliverable reports on the dissemination, communication and standardisation activities performed during the first half of INSTINCT. We revisit the strategies used to create impact related to the project outcomes and we report on the activities performed.

The dissemination, communication and standardisation efforts are part of Work Package 5 (WP5) and covers the following:

- **Dissemination:** These activities aim at raising awareness of the INSTINCT project and the results obtained in the research community. The dissemination activities are usually performed through peer-reviewed publications in conferences and journals and with the participation and organization of international events (e.g., tutorials, webinars, workshops).
- **Communication:** These efforts are related to the promotion of INSTINCT and its outcomes to the general public. Our goal is to reach the maximum number of people that know about INSTINCT and its objectives. To do this, we follow a methodology that makes the message comprehensible and simple to understand.
- **Standardisation:** The project will monitor standard development organizations to make contributions related to INSTINCT.

Performing these activities is key to maximizing the impact of the INSTINCT project results. Since the beginning of the project, we have been performing a wide range of dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities. In this deliverable we report on the activities completed so far and specify the plans for the next half of the project.

1.2 Status of this deliverable

This is the second deliverable from Work Package 5 “Dissemination, communication, standardisation and exploitation plans”. It covers the work of three tasks that comprises WP5:

- T5.1 Dissemination and communication
- T5.2 Standardisation
- T5.3 Exploitation

The first deliverable introduced the plans and strategies from all the partners to maximize the impact of the results achieved throughout the project. In this deliverable, we list the activities performed during the first half of the project, targeting the research community, industry, and general public. The next and final deliverables (D5.4 and D5.5) will report on all the activities done in the context of INSTINCT after 3 full years of work. Table 1 below summarizes the status of the deliverables of WP5.

WP5 Dissemination, communication, standardisation and exploitation		
Deliverable	Due Date	Status
D5.1 Dissemination, communication, standardisation and exploitation plans	M6	Delivered
D5.2 Interim dissemination, communication and standardisation report	M18	This deliverable
D5.3 Interim report on exploitation plans	M18	In progress
D5.4 Final dissemination, communication and standardisation report	M36	Pending
D5.5 Final report on exploitation plans	M36	Pending

Table 1: INSTINCT WP5 Deliverables.

1.3 Deliverable structure

This deliverable follows the following structure: In Section 2 we report on the Dissemination activities that have been performed since the start of the project. Section 3 describes the communication strategy that we followed, and we list the communication activities related to the project. In Section 4 we present the Exploitation and Standardisation report, with special emphasis on the individual plans. Finally, the document concludes Section 5, by briefly explaining the deliverable content and outlining the key achievements obtained so far.

2 Dissemination Report

In this section we report on all the dissemination activities performed during the first half of the INSTINCT project (i.e., M1 to M18). As a reminder, and following the dissemination plans previously described in **D5.1 “Dissemination, communication, standardisation and exploitation plans”**, INSTINCT aims to achieve two distinct types of impact:

- A profound **impact on the entire 6G technology value chain** and the future of wireless network business by realizing the vision of integrating mmWave and sub-THz communications, sensing, intelligent surfaces, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) through hardware and software demonstrators. This integration aims to create reconfigurable, immersive, energy-efficient, and interactive connectivity, transforming 6G systems into a highly adaptive and powerful environment for sensing, computing, and connectivity.
- An **impact on the fundamental building blocks of 6G networks** from both practical and scientific perspectives. This will be a result of the analysis, system concepts, models, methods, algorithms, software and hardware components developed throughout the project, bringing to fruition INSTINCT’s three core pillars.

To maximize the impact and awareness of the project’s results, the dissemination activities are focused on engaging the business ecosystem and presenting research findings to the scientific community. To do this, several INSTINCT partners are actively contributing to the IEEE ISAC, RIS and ML for Communications emerging technology initiatives (ETI).

In addition, INSTINCT dedicates part of its activities to spreading the knowledge and achievements obtained within the project to make it available to international research and industry communities. Results obtained from the research activities in the project are continuously published through articles and research papers at international conferences and workshops. In Section 2.1 “Publications” we list all the publications made so far and the ones that are currently under revision at top tier conferences and journals. The publications strategy followed by the partners aimed at maximizing the impact of the results of INSTINCT by publishing in high profile conferences and journals. Some of the top journals and magazines where we published are IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, IEEE Communications Letters, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technologies, IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society, IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security, among others. In the same section, we have also included relevant books, book chapters, and white paper written as an outcome of INSTINCT.

In addition to the conferences and journals, other related activities such as workshops and invited talks are listed in Section 2.2 “Talks, Tutorials and Events”. These activities were designed to disseminate the project results to a broader community beyond academy and research. As an example, in 2024 INSTINCT participated in the 6G Summit with a demo and pointing to the project’s website. Also, during 2024, INSTINCT travelled to Asia to give two talks at Seoul National University and at Korea Advanced Institute of Science & Technology, both in South Korea. Another example for the year 2025 is that INSTINCT organized a satellite workshop on “High-Performance

and Low-Cost Array Signal Processing" at ICASSP 2025. In addition, INSTINCT was present at EUCNC 2025 by owning a booth during the conference where several partners (i.e., Bosch, BI, I2CAT, INRIA) showed and presented results obtained during the project.

Finally, in Section 2.3 "Individual dissemination report" we list the per-partner dissemination activities and plans for the following months.

2.1 Publications

In Table 1 below, we list all the journal publications done so far as results of the efforts made in INSTINCT. In the table we can see that we have a total of 518 publications in high profile journals, including the ones that are still being reviewed, showcasing the strong commitment of all the partners to disseminate the project results and maximize the impact reached.

Journal Scientific Publications					
#	Status	Partner	Title	Authors	Journal
1	Published	I2CAT	Graph Neural Networks as an Enabler of Terahertz-based Flow-guided Nanoscale Localization over Highly Erroneous Raw Data	Calvo, G., Lemic, F., Pascual, G., Pérez, A., Struye, J., Delgado, C., Costa, X.	IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications
2	Published	I2CAT	3DSAR+: A Single-Drone 3D Cellular Search and Rescue Solution Leveraging 5G-NR	Andra Blaga, Federico Campolo, Maurizio Rea, Xavier Costa-Pérez	IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society
3	Published	CS	Efficient Beamforming and Radiation Pattern Control Using Stacked Intelligent Metasurfaces	N. U. Hassan, J. An, M. Di Renzo, M. Debbah and C. Yuen,	IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society
4	Published	CS	RIS-Assisted UAV Secure Communications With Artificial Noise-Aware Trajectory Design Against Multiple Colluding Curious Users	Y. Wen, G. Chen, S. Fang, M. Wen, S. Tomasin and M. Di Renzo	IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security

5	Published	CS	Beyond Diagonal Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces with Mutual Coupling: Modeling and Optimization	H. Li, S. Shen, M. Nerini, M. Di Renzo and B. Clerckx	IEEE Communications Letters
6	Published	CS	Beamforming Optimization for Active RIS-Aided Multiuser Communications With Hardware Impairments	Z. Peng, Z. Zhang, C. Pan, M. Di Renzo, O. A. Dobre and J. Wang	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
7	Published	CS	Indexed Multiple Access with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces: The Reflection Tuning Potential	R. Singh, A. Kaushik, W. Shin, G. C. Alexandropoulos, M. Toka and M. Di Renzo	IEEE Communications Magazine
8	Published	CS	Performance Analysis of RIS-Aided Index Modulation with Greedy Detection over Rician Fading Channels	A. Basu, S. P. Dash, A. Kaushik, D. Ghose, M. Di Renzo and Y. C. Eldar	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
9	Published	CS	Channel Estimation for Stacked Intelligent Metasurface-Assisted Wireless Networks	X. Yao, J. An, L. Gan, M. Di Renzo and C. Yuen	IEEE Wireless Communications Letters
10	Published	CS	Electromagnetic Signal and Information Theory,	M. Di Renzo and M. D. Migliore	IEEE BITS the Information Theory Magazine
11	Published	CS	Measurement-Based Small-Scale Channel Model for Sub-6 GHz RIS-Assisted Communications	J. Sang et al.	IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology
12	Published	NEC	ARES: Autonomous RIS solution with Energy harvesting	A Albanese, F Devoti, V Sciancalepore, M.	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing

			and Self-configuration towards 6G	Di Renzo, A Banchs, X Costa-Pérez	
13	Submitted	UPRC	Near-field beam shaping for 6G communications	S. Droulias, G. Stratidakis, and A. Alexiou	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
14	Published	UPRC	Bending Beams for 6G Near-Field Communications	S. Droulias, G. Stratidakis, and A. Alexiou	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
15	Published	UPRC	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces as Spatial Filters	S. Droulias, G. Stratidakis, E. Bjornson, and A. Alexiou	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
16	Published	i2CAT	5GNSS: Fusion of 5G-NR and GNSS localization for enhanced positioning accuracy and reliability	F. Campolo, A. Blaga, M. Rea, A. Lozano, X. Costa	IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technologies
17	Accepted	AAL	Model-Based Online Learning for Active ISAC Waveform Optimization	P. Pulkkinen, V. Koivunen	IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing
18	Accepted	AAL	Multicarrier ISAC: Advances in waveform design, signal processing, and learning under nonidealities	Visa Koivunen, Musa Furkan Keskin, Henk Wymeersch, Mikko Valkama, Nuria González-Prelcic	IEEE Signal Processing Magazine
19	Published	UPRC	Perceptive, Resilient, and Efficient Networks: Programming the Wireless Environment with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	Giorgos Stratidakis, Sotiris Droulias, Angeliki Alexiou	IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine

20	Published	NEC	T3DRIS: Advancing Conformal RIS Design through In-depth Analysis of Mutual Coupling Effects	Placido Mursia, Francesco Devoti, Marco Rossanese, et al.	IEEE Transactions on Communications
21	Published	i2CAT	Toward Standardized Performance Evaluation of Flow-guided Nanoscale Localization	Arnau Brosa López, Filip Lemic, Jakob Struye, et al.	IEEE Transactions on Molecular, Biological, and Multi-Scale Communications
22	Published	i2CAT	Toward Interactive Multi-User Extended Reality Using Millimeter-Wave Networking	Jakob Struye, Sam Van Damme, Nabeel Nisar Bhat, et al.	IEEE Communications Magazine
23	Accepted	i2CAT, NEC	COLoRIS: Localization-agnostic Smart Surfaces Enabling Opportunistic ISAC in 6G Networks	Guillermo Encinas-Lago, Francesco Devoti, Marco Rossanese, Vincenzo Sciancalepore, Marco Di Renzo, Xavier Costa-Pérez	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing
24	Accepted	i2CAT, NEC	RiLoCo: An ISAC-oriented AI Solution to Build RIS-empowered Networks	Guillermo Encinas-Lago, Vincenzo Sciancalepore, Henk Wymeersch, Marco Di Renzo, Xavier Costa-Pérez	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
25	Published	CS	Fluid Antenna Array Enhanced Over-the-Air Computation	Deyou Zhang, Sicong Ye, Ming Xiao, Kezhi Wang, Marco Di Renzo, Mikael Skoglund	IEEE Wireless Communications Letter
26	Published	CS	Near-Field Communications: Research Advances, Potential, and Challenges	Jiancheng An, Chau Yuen, Linglong Dai, Marco Di Renzo, Mérouane Debbah, Lajos Hanzo	IEEE Wireless Communications

27	Published	CS	Design of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces by Using S-Parameter Multiport Network Theory - Optimization and Full-Wave Validation	Andrea Abrardo, Alberto Toccafondi, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
28	Published	CS	A Universal Framework for Multiport Network Analysis of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	Matteo Nerini, Shanpu Shen, Hongyu Li, Marco Di Renzo, Bruno Clerckx	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
29	Published	CS	Deep Learning-Based Channel Extrapolation for Hybrid RIS-Aided mmWave Systems With Low-Resolution ADCs	Tingting Gong, Shun Zhang, Feifei Gao, Zan Li, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
30	Published	CS	Joint Metrics for EMF Exposure and Coverage in Real-World Homogeneous and Inhomogeneous Cellular Networks	Quentin Gontier, Charles Wiame, Shanshan Wang, Marco Di Renzo, Joe Wiart, François Horlin, Christo Tsigros, Claude Oestges, Philippe De Doncker	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
31	Published	CS	Spatially Correlated RIS-Aided Secure Massive MIMO Under CSI and Hardware Imperfections	Dan Yang, Jindan Xu, Wei Xu, Bin Sheng, Xiaohu You, Chau Yuen, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
32	Published	CS	Integrated Sensing and Communication With Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	Teng Ma, Yue Xiao, Xia Lei, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Transaction on Vehicular Technology
33	Published	CS	RIS-Assisted UAV Secure Communications	Yun Wen, Gaojie Chen, Sisai Fang, Miaowen Wen,	IEEE Transactions on Information

			With Artificial Noise-Aware Trajectory Design Against Multiple Colluding Curious Users	Stefano Tomasin, Marco Di Renzo	Forensics and Security
34	Published	CS	Joint Training and Reflection Pattern Optimization for Non-Ideal RIS-Aided Multiuser Systems	Zhenyao He, Jindan Xu, Hong Shen, Wei Xu, Chau Yuen, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Transactions on Communications
35	Published	CS	Intelligent Surfaces Empowered Wireless Network: Recent Advances and the Road to 6G	Qingqing Wu, Beixiong Zheng, Changsheng You, Lipeng Zhu, Kaiming Shen, Xiaodan Shao, Weidong Mei, Boya Di, Hongliang Zhang, Ertugrul Basar, Lingyang Song, Marco Di Renzo, Zhi-Quan Luo, Rui Zhang	Proceedings of the IEEE
36	Published	CS	Two-Dimensional Direction-of-Arrival Estimation Using Stacked Intelligent Metasurfaces	Jiancheng An, Chau Yuen, Yong Liang Guan, Marco Di Renzo, Mérouane Debbah, H. Vincent Poor, Lajos Hanzo	IEEE Journal of Selected Areas in Communications
37	Published	CS	Integrated Sensing and Communications for IoT: Synergies with Key 6G Technology Enablers	Aryan Kaushik, Rohit Singh, Ming Li, Honghao Luo, Shalanika Dayarathna, Rajitha Senanayake, Xueli An, Richard A. Stirling-Gallacher, Wonjae Shin, and Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Internet of Things Magazine
38	Published	CS	Intelligent Reflecting Surface Assisted mmWave	Zhengyu Zhu, Zheng Li, Zheng Chu, Yingying Guan, Qingqing Wu, Pei	IEEE Internet of Things Journal

			Integrated Sensing and Communication Systems	Xiao, Marco Di Renzo, Inkyu Lee	
39	Published	CS	Toward Integrated Sensing and Communications for 6G: Key Enabling Technologies, Standardisation, and Challenges	Aryan Kaushik, Rohit Singh, Shalanika Dayarathna, Rajitha Senanayake, Marco Di Renzo, Miguel Dajer, Hyungju Ji, Younsun Kim, Vincenzo Sciancalepore, Alessio Zappone, Wonjae Shin	IEEE Communications Standards Magazine
40	Published	CS	Terahertz Communications and Sensing for 6G and Beyond: A Comprehensive Review	Wei Jiang, Qiheng Zhou, Jiguang He, Mohammad Asif Habibi, Sergiy Melnyk, Mohammed El-Absi, Bin Han, Marco Di Renzo, Hans Dieter Schotten, Fa-Long Luo, Tarek S. El-Bawab, Markku J. Juntti, Mérouane Debbah, Victor C. M. Leung	IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials
41	Published	CS	Fingerprinting Database Development Methods for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface Assisted Indoor Positioning System	Aisha Javed, Naveed Ul Hassan, Ammar Rafique, Muhammad Zubair, Marco Di Renzo, Chau Yuen	IEEE Access
42	Published	CS	Rate Region of RIS-Aided URLLC Broadcast Channels: Diagonal Versus Beyond Diagonal Globally Passive RIS	Mohammad Soleymani, Alessio Zappone, Eduard A. Jorswieck, Marco Di Renzo, Ignacio Santamaría	IEEE Wireless Communications Letters

43	Published	CS	Flexible Intelligent Metasurfaces for Downlink Multiuser MISO Communications	Jiancheng An, Chau Yuen, Marco Di Renzo, Mérouane Debbah, H. Vincent Poor, Lajos Hanzo	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
44	Published	CS	Spatial Multiplexing in Near-Field Line-of-Sight MIMO Communications: Paraxial and Non-Paraxial Deployments	Juan Carlos Ruiz Sicilia, Marco Di Renzo, Placido Mursia, Aryan Kaushik, Vincenzo Sciancalepore	IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking
45	Published	CS	T3DRIS: Advancing Conformal RIS Design Through In-Depth Analysis of Mutual Coupling Effects	Placido Mursia, Francesco Devoti, Marco Rossanese, Vincenzo Sciancalepore, Gabriele Gradoni, Marco Di Renzo, Xavier Costa-Pérez	IEEE Transactions on Communications
46	Published	CS	Active Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Based Symbiotic Radio: Boosting Mutual Benefits	Ruizhe Long, Ying-Chang Liang, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking
47	Published	CS	Next Generation Advanced Transceiver Technologies for 6G and Beyond	Changsheng You, Yunlong Cai, Yuanwei Liu, Marco Di Renzo, Tolga M. Duman, Aylin Yener, A. Lee Swindlehurst	IEEE Journal of Selected Areas in Communications
48	Published	CS	Quantum-Enhanced DRL Optimization for DoA Estimation and Task Offloading in ISAC Systems	Anal Paul, Keshav Singh, Aryan Kaushik, Chih-Peng Li, Octavia A. Dobre, Marco Di Renzo, Trung Q. Duong	IEEE Journal of Selected Areas in Communications
49	Published	CS	Cooperative Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access With	Jun Li, Shuping Dang, Xuan Chen, Miaowen Wen, Marco	IEEE Journal of Selected Areas in Communications

			Index Modulation for Air-Ground Multi-UAV Networks	Di Renzo, Huseyin Arslan	
50	Published	UPRC	Near-Field Hierarchical Localization for Integrated Sensing and Communication	Giorgos Stratidakis, Sotiris Droulias, Angeliki Alexiou	IEEE Access
51	Published	UPRC	Orthogonal beams and codebook design for near-field space division multiple access in 6G systems	Sotiris Droulias, Giorgos Stratidakis, Angeliki Alexiou	IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation

Table 2: Journal Scientific Contributions.

In Table 2 below we show a similar list but with the publications made in scientific conferences. A total of 23 articles were submitted to top-tier conferences.

Conference Scientific Publications					
#	Status	Partner	Title	Authors	Conference
1	Published	INRIA	Multi-Site Wireless Channel Charting Through Latent Space Alignment	Yamil E Vindas Yassine, Maxime Guillaud	IEEE SPAWC
2	Published	I2CAT	Multi-Gigabit Interactive Extended Reality Over Millimeter-Wave: An End-To-End System Approach	Jakob Struye, Filip Lemic, Jeroen Famaey	IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)
3	Submitted	UPRC	Beam focusing in near-field communications: enhancing the physical layer security	S. Droulias, G. Stratidakis, and A. Alexiou	IEEE SPAWC
4	Accepted	GW	5G mmWave RIS-Based User Localization Using Side Link Communication Protocols	A. Toubal, A. Shokair, T. McGarry, J. de Rosny, Y. Nasser, G. Lerosey	IEEE EuCNC

5	Published	AAL	Cognitive Beamspace Algorithm for Integrated Sensing and Communications	Petteri Pulkkinen, Majdoddin Esfandiari, Visa Koivunen	IEEE Radar Conference
6	Published	AAL	Partially Observable Model-Based Learning FOR ISAC Resource Allocation	Petteri Pulkkinen, Visa Koivunen	IEEE ICASSP
7	Published	AAL	Generative Deep Synthesis of MIMO Sensing Waveforms with Desired Transmit Beampattern	Vesa Saarinen, Robin Rajamäki, Visa Koivunen	2024 Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers
8	Published	AAL	SPARSE ARRAY SENSOR SELECTION IN ISAC WITH IDENTIFIABILITY GUARANTEES	Robin Rajamäki, Piya Pal	Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers
9	Published	AAL	JOINTLY OPTIMAL ARRAY GEOMETRIES AND WAVEFORMS IN ACTIVE SENSING: NEW INSIGHTS INTO ARRAY DESIGN VIA THE CRAMÉR-RAO BOUND	Ids van der Werf, Geert Leus, Robin Rajamäki	2025 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)
10	Published	AAL	Beamspace and Frequency Domain ISAC Resource Allocation Using Reinforcement Learning	Petteri Pulkkinen, Majdoddin Esfandiari, Visa Koivunen	2024 Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers

11	Published	AAL	AdaBoost-Based Channel Estimation in One-Bit Millimeter-Wave MIMO	Petteri Pulkkinen, Majdoddin Esfandiari, Sergiy Vorobyov, Visa Koivunen	2025 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)
12	Published	Inria	How Much Can Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Augment Sky Visibility: A Stochastic Geometry Approach	J. Lee and F. Baccelli	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications
13	Submitted	Inria	Stochastic Geometry and Dynamical System Analysis of Walker Constellation Networks	Chang-Sik Choi, Bon-Jun Ku, Francois Baccelli	IEEE
14	Submitted	TID	From Waves to Graphs: A Ray-Tracing-Inspired Neural Radio Propagation Model	Paul Almasan, et al.	IEEE
15	Accepted	i2CAT	Leveraging 5G-NR for Finding Mobile Devices with UAVs: Latency vs Accuracy Trade-off	Andra Blaga, Federico Campolo, Filip Lemic, Oriol Sallent, Xavier Costa-Pérez	IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)
16	Published	CS	Multi-user ISAC through Stacked Intelligent Metasurfaces: New Algorithms and Experiments	Ziqing Wang, Hongzheng Liu, Jianan Zhang, Rujing Xiong, Kai Wan, Xuewen Qian, Marco Di Renzo, Robert Caiming Qiu	IEEE Global Communications Conference: Selected Areas in Communications: Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces

17	Published	CS	Secrecy Energy Efficiency Maximization in RIS-Aided Wireless Networks	Robert Kuku Fotoock, Alessio Zappone, Marco Di Renzo	IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC): SAC Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces and Smart Environments Track
18	Published	CS	Secrecy Energy Efficiency Maximization in RIS-Aided Wireless Networks with Statistical CSI	Robert Kuku Fotoock, Agbotiname Lucky Imoize, Alessio Zappone, Marco Di Renzo, Roberto Garelo	IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)
19	Published	CS	Energy Efficiency Comparison of RIS Architectures in MISO Broadcast Channels	Mohammad Soleymani, Ignacio Santamaría, Eduard A. Jorswieck, Marco Di Renzo, Jesús Gutiérrez	IEEE 25th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)
20	Accepted	GW	Experimental Approach to Adaptive RIS-Based Beam Tracking and User Localization in 5G mmWave Networks	A. Toubal, A. Shokair, R. Bombardelli, T. mcGary, Y. Nasser, J. DeRosny, G. Lerosey	IEEE EuCNC
21	Published	Inria	Dynamic Channel Charting: Integrating Online Sample Selection with Continual Learning	Y. Vindas, M. Guillaud	IEEE ICC 2025

			for Streaming CSI Data		
22	Published	Inria	Multi-cell Outdoor Channel State Information Dataset (MOCSID)	M. Makhlof, M. Guillaud, Y. Vindas	EuCNC 2025
23	Published	TID	AI-Powered Data Synthesis for Advanced Simulation in 5G/6G mmWave Integrated Access and Backhaul Networks	Amir Ashtari G.; Farhad Rezazadeh; Marco Giordani; Sandra Lagén; Lingjia Liu; Andra Lutu	2025 Annual Conference on Wireless On Demand Network Systems and Services (WONS)
24	Published	UPRC	Beam-focusing in near-field communications: enhancing the physical layer security	Sotiris Droulias, Giorgos Stratidakis, Angeliki Alexiou	International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)
25	Accepted	UPRC	Beam-focusing Based Hierarchical Localization and Tracking in Angle and Range	Giorgos Stratidakis, Sotiris Droulias, Angeliki Alexiou	IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)

Table 3: Conference Scientific Publications.

In the last table from this section, Table 3, we list the book chapters and white papers that are related to the INSTINCT project.

Book Chapters					
#	Status	Partner	Title	Authors	Book/Title
1	Published	I2CAT	Location-based real-time utilization of reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for mmWave integrated communication and sensing in full-	Filip Lemic, Jalal Jalali, Gerard Calvo Bartra, et al.	IET Book "Advanced Metaverse Wireless Communication Systems"

			immersive multiuser Metaverse scenarios		
2	Accepted	AAL	Model-based reinforcement learning for ISAC	Petteri Pulkkinen, Visa Koivunen	"Machine learning for radar signal processing" by Wiley-IEEE
3	Published	NEC, BI, UPRC, i2CAT, GW	Contribution to the Chapter 4: 6G ARCHITECTURE	Francesco Devoti, Padmanava Sen, Sotiris Droulias, Filip Lemic, Youssef Nasser	6G-IA Vision Working Group White Paper "European Vision for the 6G Network Ecosystem"

Table 4: Books, Books Chapters and White Papers.

2.2 Talks, Tutorials and Events

#	Name	Type of activity	Target audience	Objective(s)	Status	Date
1	Demo in Dresden 6G Summit 2024	Conf.	Research communities Industry, business partners, National authorities, Innovators	Showing a demo with a link to INSTINCT.	Delivered	14.05.2024
2	Tutorial at ICC 2024	Conf.	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Tutorial on "When the Sensing sphere touches Communication and Electromagnetism: The academic, industrial and standard perspectives." Presenting ISAC in industrial and standardisation perspectives.	Delivered	13.06.2024
3	INSTINCT Workshop at JC&S Symposium 2025	Conf.	Research communities, Specific end user communities, Innovators	Tutorial on "When the Sensing sphere touches Communication and Electromagnetism: The academic, industrial and standard perspectives."	Delivered	19.03.2024

				Presenting ISAC in industrial and standardisation perspectives.		
4	Invited talk at ERICSSON R&D	Meetings	Research communities, EU Institutions	Invited talk on Wireless Channel Charting for Next-Generation Radio Access Networks. Introducing the INSTINCT project, its scope, and current results.	Delivered	21.06.2024
5	Demo in JC&S Symposium	Conf.	Research communities	Showing a demonstrator at the JC&S Symposium with a link to INSTINCT project.	Delivered	19.03.2024
6	Tutorial in JC&S Symposium	Conf.	Research communities	Tutorial in JC&S Symposium with a link to INSTINCT.	Delivered	19.03.2025
7	Invited talk at Linköping University	Education and training events	Research communities	Invited talk on Wireless Channel Charting for Next-Generation Radio Access Networks. Introducing self-supervised sensing tools.	Delivered	24.09.2024
8	ComSoc distinguished lecture in Fortaleza	Meetings	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Invited talk on Wireless Channel Charting for Next-Generation Radio Access Networks. Introducing self-supervised sensing tools.	Delivered	12.07.2024
9	ComSoc distinguished lecture, Sao Jose dos Campos	Meetings	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Invited talk on Wireless Channel Charting for Next-Generation Radio Access Networks in Brazil.	Delivered	10.07.2025
10	Invited talk at Princeton University, NJ, USA	Meetings	Research communities	Invited talk on ISAC, waveform design, and optimization with a link to INSTINCT.	Delivered	no date
11	Invited talk on Channel Charting in India	Meetings	Research communities	Invited talk on Channel Charting: Self-Supervised Learning for Wireless Propagation at Indian Institute of Information Technology and Management, Gwalior.	Delivered	11.12.2024

				Introducing self-supervised sensing tools.		
12	Invited talk on use of ISAC in Logistic Use Cases	Conf.	Research communities, Industry, business partners, National authorities, Innovators	Showing benefits of ISAC in vertical applications	Delivered	03.07.2024
13	Invited talk at Lockheed-Martin, NJ, USA	Meetings	Industry, business partners	Invited talk on ISAC, waveform design, and optimization. Showing connection to INSTINCT.	Delivered	no date
14	Invited talk at Rutgers University and WINLAB, NJ,	Meetings	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Invited talk on ISAC, waveform design, and optimization. Showing the connection with the INSTINCT project.	Delivered	no date
15	Invited talk at Temple University, PA, USA	Meetings	Research communities	Invited talk on ISAC, waveform design and optimization with a link to INSTINCT.	Delivered	no date
16	Invited talk at Nokia Bell Labs, Murray Hill, NJ,	Meetings	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Invited talk on ISAC, waveform design, and optimization with a link to INSTINCT project.	Delivered	no date
17	Tutorial at ISWCS conference 2024	Conf.	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Tutorial on Wireless Channel Charting for Next-Generation Radio Access Networks. Introducing self-supervised sensing tools.	Delivered	14.07.2024
18	Workshop at EUCNC	Meetings	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Introducing the INSTINCT project and its scope. Presentation on Terahertz Communications in EU SNS JU Projects.	Delivered	03.06.2024

19	Invited talk on RIS for 6G	Meetings	Research communities	Presenting RIS for 6G: A fast track to perceptive networks with an introduction to the INSTINCT project.	Delivered	23.02.2024
20	Zenodo	Other	EU Institutions, Research communities, Industry, business partners	In order to contribute to open science, we are publishing all of our findings on Zenodo.	Ongoing	Updated regularly
21	Workshop at EUCNC 2025	Meetings	Research communities	Workshop on NTN	Ongoing	03.06.2025
22	Invited talk at SNU-South Korea	Meetings	Research communities	Invited talk on dynamics in cellular networks	Delivered	28.11.2024
23	Invited Talk at KAIST, South Korea	Meetings	Research communities	Invited talk on mastering complexity in 6G	Delivered	16.11.2024
24	Invited Talk at WWRHuddle, Berlin, Germany	Meetings	Research communities	Invited talk on wideband JCAS	Delivered	19.04.2024
25	Workshop Talk at IEEE JC&S Symposium, Oulu, Finland	Conference	Research communities	Workshop talk on wideband JCAS	Delivered	28.01.2025
26	Panel at WCNC 2025, Milan	Conferences	Research communities	Panel on: Future Perceptive Networks empowered by Integrated Sensing and Communications: Spectrum Aspects, Energy Efficiency, Infrastructures and Business Models	Delivered	26.03.2025

27	Special Session at Asilomar 2025	Conferences	Research Communities	Organized special session on "Machine Learning for Integrated Sensing and Communications"	Delivered	28.10.2024
28	Satellite workshop at ICASSP 2025	Conference	Research Communities	Organized satellite workshop on "High-Performance and Low-Cost Array Signal Processing" at ICASSP 2025	Delivered	07.04.2025
29	Nato SET ISAC work group	Other	Research Communities	Chairing Nato SET work group on ISAC	Ongoing	
30	Tutorial at ICMLCN 2025 conference	Conferences	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Tutorial on Wireless Channel Charting for Next-Generation Radio Access Networks. Introducing self-supervised sensing tools.	Delivered	26.05.2025

Table 5: Talks, tutorials and events related to INSTINCT

2.2.1 INSTINCT at EUCNC 2025

INSTINCT was present at EUCNC 2025 in Poznan, Poland. This was a 4-day event in June where several INSTINCT partners presented their results and vision within the scope of the project. This activity helped position the project among other EU projects and outline its ambitious goals for JSAC/ISAC.

Figure 1: INSTINCT project members at EUCNC 2025 in booth #51.

INSTINCT was present at Booth #51, where we proudly showcased three of our four demonstrators, offering a tangible look at our groundbreaking work. Visitors also got a comprehensive overview of our key research achievements through a dedicated video presentation. Beyond the booth, INSTINCT was actively represented in several key sessions, sharing our expertise and contributing to vital discussions. The hands-on demos by our partners Barkhausen Institut and INSA Lyon - Institut National des Sciences Appliquées de Lyon, along with the video demonstration by i2CAT Research Centre, University of Piraeus Research Center (UPRC), and Inria, offered a firsthand look at the revolutionary impact of INSTINCT's 6G pillars.

Figure 2: Booth #51 with the screen displaying the INSTINCT partners.

During the event, a flyer was distributed among the attendees with key information about the project and contact points or links to learn more about it. Figure 3 shows an image of the flyer.

Figure 3: INSTINCT Flyer used at EUCNC 2025.

2.3 Individual dissemination report

In the following, we detail the individual dissemination report and future plans for all the INSTINCT partners:

BI: As a research institute, will disseminate the project results at Tier-1 conferences (namely, Globecom, ICC, VTC-Spring, JC&S Symposium, EUCNC) as well as in high impact journals (e.g., IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, IEEE Signal processing Magazine, IEEE TCAS) and workshops. Furthermore, BI regularly showcases technology demonstrators at high outreach exhibitions (e.g. IEEE JC&S Symposium, IEEE 6G Summit at Dresden) to address academic and

industrial stakeholders. In 2023 and 2024, joint communication and sensing demonstrators are shown to these two above mentioned conferences/summits triggering meaningful discussions and interest among the attendees. BI also plans to foster collaborations with German national funded 6G projects like Komsens-6G and ICAS4Mobility in order to promote INSTINCT project results to influential and relevant stakeholders in Germany. The yearly Berlin-6G conference and EUCNC conference are two other events, BI would like to focus in coming years.

UPRC: Has made several contributions by submitting scientific articles to journals and conferences such as IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications or IEEE SPAWC. UPRC plans to disseminate INSTINCT findings by contributing to high profile conferences focusing on communications and networks, such as IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC), IEEE International Workshop on Signal processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC), and European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC). Furthermore, UPRC plans to submit papers to high profile journals and magazines in the networking and communication field, such as IEEE Transactions (on Communications, Wireless Communications, Vehicular Technology, Antennas and Propagation, etc.), IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications (JCS), IEEE Communications Magazine and IEEE Wireless Magazine.

BOSCH: Bosch has disseminated the project results at EUCNC by presenting the outcomes of WP1 and WP4 work, which Bosch leads. In addition, Andreas Müller contributed to various keynotes in Hannover Messe and EUCNC. BOSCH actively supports dissemination activities by engaging with regulators and policymakers and participating in standardisation bodies and industry alliances such as 3GPP, ITU, 5G-ACIA, 5GAA, and ETSI.

AAL: AAL primarily disseminated research results via scientific publications. Researchers participated in conferences, workshops, seminars, NATO S&T panels in order to disseminate the results of the project. Aalto is also among founders of a NATO working groups on ISAC and cognitive radar. Aalto is also disseminating results through IEEE ISAC activity, in particular new IEEE conference series on ISAC, that is joint effort among the Communications Society, Signal Processing Society as well as Aerospace and Electronic Systems Society where most of the radar research is done. Aalto organized a special session on ISAC in the 2024 Radar Conference in Denver, Colorado, and 2024 Asilomar Conference in Pacific Grove, CA, contributed to ISAC and machine learning related special session in IEEE ICASSP 2024 in Seoul, Korea, as well as co-organized a satellite workshop on “High-Performance and Low-Cost Array Signal Processing” at ICASSP 2025, Hyderabad, India. Aalto has also published a paper on ISAC related reinforcement learning in an ISAC special issue of the IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing, and a paper on Multicarrier ISAC in the IEEE Signal Processing Magazine, special issue on ISAC. A book chapter on “Model-based reinforcement learning for ISAC” will be published in a book on “Machine learning for radar signal processing” by Wiley-IEEE. Conference publications have appeared in the proceedings of Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers 2024, IEEE RadarConf 2024, and IEEE ICASSP 2025. Prof. Koivunen has given invited talks in the US on ISAC at Rutgers University and WINLAB, NJ, Nokia-Bell Labs, Murray Hill, NJ, Princeton University, NJ, and Temple University, PA. In the coming months, manuscripts related to INSTINCT will be submitted

to the IEEE SPAWC 2025, EUSIPCO 2025, and Asilomar 2025 conferences, as well as the IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing.

FHG-HHI: FHG-HHI disseminated results of the project to the scientific community by contributing a talk to the INSTINCT Special Session at the JC&S symposium in Oulu in January 2025. Additionally, an invited talk on wideband JCAS was delivered at the WWRF Huddle conference in Berlin in April 2024.

GW: GW has actively contributed to the dissemination activities of the project through the publication of conference papers. Also, GW is preparing a demo for EuCNC and will continue to push the demonstrations of RIS in major international events. GW has also participated in the panel at WCNC on ISAC. In addition, GW took part in invited talk in major academic events.

NEC: NEC is actively contributing to the project's dissemination and communication activities, primarily through scientific publications and participation in conferences, tutorials, and workshops. It has also coordinated the collection and provision of project inputs for the 6G-IA white paper titled "European Vision for the 6G Network Ecosystem." In addition, NEC is leading Task 5.2 on standardisation and plans to actively contribute to standardisation efforts as one of the industrial partners aiming at ETSI RIS and ETSI ISAC in particular. NEC intends to continue its active involvement in both dissemination and standardisation activities throughout the project.

INRIA: Inria's main activities thus far include dissemination through scientific publications. Dr. Guillaud gave tutorials on self-supervised methods for sensing in the ISWCS 2024 and ICMLCN 2025 conferences, as well as IEEE ComSoc distinguished lectures and invited seminars in Europe and beyond (Germany, Sweden, Brazil, India). During these events, which are subsequently shared on social media individually and through the INSTINCT project, the team and / or financing body is visible and highlighted. Interactions with industrial partners (major equipment manufacturers) also took place during which project results were presented. A live demonstration involving the remote radio infrastructure of CortexLab was performed at EuCNC 2025. Inria was also co-organizer of conference special sessions related to the project's objectives at the Asilomar 2024 and 2025 conferences. Inria will explore the best ways to further disseminate to fellow researchers and industrial organizations within and beyond the INSTINCT project.

INSA Lyon: INSA Lyon coordinates with Inria on dissemination activities and thus similarly INSA Lyon researchers' scientific publications, conferences or research stays have been welcome opportunities to pursue these tasks. This includes work on CortexLab (part of Inria / INSA Lyon's CITI laboratory) and any activities to highlight it and demonstrate to researchers, industry and the general public collaborations using this platform.

i2CAT: As the leader of Task 5.1 on dissemination and communication, i2CAT is implementing a comprehensive strategy to share the project's findings and impact. This includes actively contributing to the dissemination of research findings through the publication of scientific papers in high-impact journals and presentations at top conferences, thereby reaching a specialized academic audience. Furthermore, to ensure open science practices and the long-term scientific preservation of project outputs, i2CAT has created an INSTINCT Zenodo Community, where all partners are ensuring their uploads. Looking ahead, i2CAT plans to

continue proactive and timely dissemination through a content calendar aligned with upcoming project milestones and deliverables. i2CAT's commitment remains to ensuring dissemination efforts effectively communicate the value and impact of the project to the scientific community through publications and online presence, while also continuing to produce scientific journal papers.

UOulu: UOulu hosted the 5th IEEE International Symposium on Joint Communications & Sensing on January 28 – 30, 2025. The results of the research done at UOulu will be published in scientific conferences and journals.

CS-UPS: CS has actively contributed to the dissemination activities of the project through the publication of journal and conference papers. Also, CS delivered short courses, invited presentations, and tutorials at major international events worldwide, notably IEEE conferences. In addition, CS took part in invited academic and industrial panels and workshops at IEEE conferences, which were focused on project activities.

TID/TSA: TID and TSA actively contribute to the dissemination activities with publications in high profile conferences and journals. In addition, TSA has contributed to the open-source community by implementing a code to load antenna radiation patterns in Sionna RT (<https://nvlabs.github.io/sionna/rt/index.html>). The code is publicly available in https://github.com/rolytel/antenna_pattern_msi_importer. TID and TSA are committed to continue contributing to the dissemination activities through several ongoing efforts that are expected to finalize in scientific publications.

3 Communication Report

The communication activities performed aimed at promoting project results to a wide audience. To maximize impact, the project's communication strategy objectives defined in **D5.1 "Dissemination, communication, standardisation and exploitation plans"** were:

- raise awareness and ensure maximum visibility of the project key facts, objectives, activities, and findings among civil society,
- announce and promote INSTINCT events and dissemination material,
- foster engagement and support from the public, industry and academia, and
- support the dissemination, standardisation and exploitation objectives.

To meet these objectives, INSTINCT used a combination of modern communication tools and channels to reach the maximum audience. Initially, INSTINCT developed a set of distinctive materials to reflect a unique identity for all communication and dissemination activities. For example, a project logo, infographics, a website (<http://instinct-6g.eu/>), and a promotional video, among others, were created during the initial months of the project. In addition, a LinkedIn account was created to communicate project related activities (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-instinct/>).

Since the inception of INSTINCT, the project employs a variety of communication tools tailored to effectively engage a wide and diverse audience. Initially, materials such as merchandising, infographics, logos, and multimedia material were created during the first months of the project. More information on the first communication efforts can be found in deliverable **D5.1 "Dissemination, communication, standardisation and exploitation plans"**. Since then, digital channels have been used intensively to bring the project closer to all audiences and the public. Below we summarize the different digital channels used to communicate project results and events:

- **Project website (<http://instinct-6g.eu/>):** The project website is the primary asset for promoting project-related activities and results. The final version was finished in M6 and is being maintained and updated regularly with publications (with access to published scientific articles), contact information and a FAQ section. In section 3.1.1 "Project website" we report on the website traffic activity by showing the number of visitors and the most frequent outgoing traffic.
- **Corporate contact point:** INSTINCT set up a corporate contact point to all stakeholders (instinct-info@barkhauseninstitut.org), with a 72-hour reply commitment, that manages general inquiries, collaboration requests, bug-tracking and feature requests.
- **Social media (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-instinct/>):** INSTINCT is posting regular content in the LinkedIn social network. This is a professional channel that helps the dissemination and communication of news, results, events, etc. In section 3.1.2 "LinkedIn" we report the activities performed in the social network and we analyze the impact INSTINCT is having.
- **Newsletter:** INSTINCT prepared a newsletter to broadcast the main activities.

- **Press release:** INSTINCT prepared a joint press release to present the project and introduce the partners. The document was used by the INSTINCT partners as part of their communication strategies, reaching out to their network of customers and members.

3.1 Digital Channels

3.1.1 Project website

During the initial stages of the project, we built a website (<http://instinct-6g.eu/>) as the first step towards promoting project related activities and results to all the targeted audiences. Since then, we have been improving the website by adding more content. For example, we have been adding news related to the project in the “News” section and we have been listing all the publications related to INSTINCT in the “Publications” section. Figure 4 below shows a screenshot of the latter.

Overview of all publications

- S. Al Nahiyani, M. Ramzan, S. Kamal and P. Sen, "Passive Artificial Magnetic Conductor (AMC) Reflector for Far-Field Beam Steering", 2024 54th European Microwave Conference (EuMC), Paris, France, 2024, pp. 533-536, doi: 10.23919/EuMC61614.2024.10732568. [Link to document](#)
- A. Blaga, F. Campolo, M. Rea and X. Costa-Pérez, "3DSAR+: A Single-Drone 3D Cellular Search and Rescue Solution Leveraging 5G-NR", *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 4808-4822, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2024.3437681. [Link to document](#)
- F. Campolo, A. Blaga, M. Rea, X. Costa-Pérez and A. Lozano, "5GNSS: Fusion of 5G-NR and GNSS Localization for Enhanced Positioning Accuracy and Reliability", 2024, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2024.3396991. [Link to document](#)
- A. Albanese, F. Devoti, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, A. Banchs and X. Costa-Pérez, "ARES: Autonomous RIS Solution With Energy Harvesting and Self-Configuration Towards 6G", 2024, doi: 10.1109/TMC.2024.3405076. [Link to document](#)
- Z. Peng, Z. Zhang, C. Pan, M. D. Renzo, O. A. Dobre and J. Wang, "Beamforming Optimization for Active RIS-Aided Multiuser Communications With Hardware Impairments", *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 9884-9898, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TWC.2024.3367131. [Link to document](#)
- H. Li, S. Shen, M. Nerini, M. Di Renzo and B. Clerckx, "Beyond Diagonal Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces With Mutual Coupling: Modeling and Optimization", *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 937-941, 2024, doi: 10.1109/LCOMM.2024.3361648. [Link to document](#)
- X. Yao, J. An, L. Gan, M. Di Renzo and C. Yuen, "Channel Estimation for Stacked Intelligent Metasurface-Assisted Wireless Networks", *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1349-1353, 2024, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2024.3369874. [Link to document](#)
- N. U. Hassan, J. An, M. Di Renzo, M. Debbah and C. Yuen, "Efficient Beamforming and Radiation Pattern Control Using Stacked Intelligent Metasurfaces", *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 599-611, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2023.3349155. [Link to document](#)
- G. Calvo Bartra, F. Lemic, G. Pascual, A. Pérez, J. Struye, Ca. Delgado Pinillos and X. Costa-Pérez, "Graph Neural Networks as an Enabler of Terahertz-Based Flow-Guided Nanoscale Localization Over Highly Erroneous Raw Data", *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 42, no. 8, pp. 1992-2008, 2024, doi: 10.1109/JSAC.2024.3399257. [Link to document](#)

Figure 4: Overview of the "Publications" section in the INSTINCT website.

We have also been analyzing the traffic to the website to understand better the impact and reach of INSTINCT. In Figure 5 below, we can see the incoming/outgoing traffic statistics of the project website. We can observe that the incoming traffic comes from different sources such as other websites, search engines and social networks. In the same figure, we can see that most of the outlinks lead towards content related to the project LinkedIn account, paper publications, and partners' own websites.

Figure 5: INSTINCT website incoming/outgoing traffic distribution.

Figure 6 below shows the geographic distribution of incoming traffic to the website. The results come from all over the world, being the United States of America the country that has more visitors to the project website. It is important to note that website tracking is only available when the visitors explicitly consent to it. As a result, the real numbers of incoming/outgoing traffic would be higher, and the geographic distribution could change.

Figure 6: INSTINCT website geographic traffic source.

During the next months of the project, we will keep updating the project website regularly to include the latest news and results of the project.

3.1.2 Social media

INSTINCT partners have also set up a LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-instinct>) with more than 470 subscriptions by the time of writing this deliverable. Figure 7 shows

the INSTINCT LinkedIn account with the total number of followers. This shows an interest of the community in the INSTINCT project, but also satisfies one of our communications KPIs, which aimed at reaching 150 members. Regular posts are being carefully prepared, following a detailed agenda that includes the organization and participation in events (see Figure 8) and dissemination of publications (see Figure 9), among others. We have already published 50 posts, aiming at reaching soon our second dissemination KPI by posting more than 60 posts. In Figure 10 we report the highlights of the INSTINCT LinkedIn account. As can be seen, the account has reached more than 45000 impressions and more than 800 reactions. During the next months, we plan to proceed with the LinkedIn posts to give more visibility to all the activities related to the project.

Figure 7: Screenshot of INSTINCT's LinkedIn main page.

Figure 8: Screenshot of INSTINCT LinkedIn posts related to events.

Figure 9: Screenshot of INSTINCT LinkedIn post disseminating a publication related to the project.

Figure 10: Highlights of the INSTINCT LinkedIn.

In Figure 11, we show the evolution of the number of clicks to any of the posts made using the INSTINCT account since its creation. These clicks include the number of clicks on the account’s content and company logo by a signed-in member. Information not included in this number are interactions, reposts, reactions, and comments. If a member clicks on a document multiple times, it counts as a single click. The graphic indicates a large number of clicks of the community with the content of the INSTINCT account.

Finally, Figure 12 shows the number of impressions over time. An impression is when the content (i.e., post, article) appears on a LinkedIn user’s feed, regardless of whether they engage or not. This metric measures the content’s visibility and reach. Therefore, we can see that the content of INSTINCT reaches the scale of hundreds of impressions regularly, indicating that we are reaching a large part of the general audience.

Figure 11: INSTINCT LinkedIn number of clicks over time.

Figure 12: INSTINCT LinkedIn number of impressions over time.

3.1.3 Newsletter

The INSTINCT partners have prepared a quarterly newsletter to broadcast the activities done within the scope of the project. The first newsletter contains an overview of the INSTINCT project, the list of partners, a summary of the different work packages with relevant updates, the major events that the project was part of, and a list of publications made as an outcome of the project.

The newsletter can be found in the project website in <https://www.barkhauseninstitut.org/en/instinct-joint-sensing-and-communication-for-future-connectivity/default-da1513c64f358a94cf2065130ad69fd7>. The figure below shows the first page of the newsletter. The quarterly newsletter (Q1 2025) is linked [here](#).

INSTINCT Newsletter Q1 2025

Project Overview	
Project name, short and extensive	INSTINCT (Joint Sensing and Communications for Future Interactive, Immersive, and Intelligent Connectivity Beyond Communications)
Name of Coordinator, Company of coordinator	Padmanava Sen (Barkhausen Institut gGmbH) Contact
Technical Manager	Angeliki Alexiou (University of Piraeus - Research Center)
Start date-End date of the project	January 2024 – December 2026
Website	http://instinct-6g.eu/
LinkedIn account	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-instinct/
Verticals concerned (see list below)	Wireless Communication Technologies and Signal Processing, Joint communication and sensing
List of partners	Barkhausen Institut, University of Piraeus - Research Center, Bosch, Aalto University, Fraunhofer HHI, Greenerwave, NEC Laboratories Europe, Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et Automatique, Institut National des Sciences Appliquées de Lyon, i2CAT Foundation, Oulu University, Centralesupelec, Telefónica (TID), Teleónica (TSA)

Contributors in this Newsletter: Researchers in the consortium

E-mail: instinct-info@barkhauseninstitut.orgFollow us on LinkedIn: [SNS INSTINCT 6G](#)

Sign up here for the newsletter below:

Figure 13: Front page of the newsletter for Q1 2025.

3.2 Individual communication report

In the following, we detail the individual communication report for all the INSTINCT partners:

BI: BI communicated project results through LinkedIn pages of BI and the project INSTINCT. BI also regularly participates in public outreach events like “Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften” or “Girls’ Day”. At the same time, BI has several public outreach programs like learning labs and COSMO science forum in Dresden. Several events open to the public are coordinated by BI and research concepts are showcased. The COSMO space is operated jointly by the Barkhausen Institut and the Department for Speculative Transformation at TU Dresden in cooperation with many partners.

UPRC: UPRC plans to communicate the project findings and activities through the University of Piraeus communication channels and social media, such as LinkedIn. In addition to reaching out to the research community (through UPRC's participation in research collaborations, conferences and research fora), UPRC is a close collaborator of the Greek regulator, ETSI organization members and ITU-R members and officers and a regular participant and contributor to these organizations' activities/initiatives. Sending information by email to relevant lists and sharing printed or electronic material with these communities will increase INSTINCT visibility and raise awareness on INSTINCT results.

BOSCH: Bosch has actively communicated the project findings and scope within other internal stakeholders within the company. Bosch is also active in multiple standardisation and regulation bodies, see table 6.

AAL: Communicated results of the project to the scientific community via publishing in top-tier journals, presenting at international conferences, and giving invited talks at university and industry partners (see Section 2.3). Publications were publicized to the professional community via the INSTINCT LinkedIn channel.

FHG-HHI: Presented the INSTINCT project as one of its forward-looking activities at its booth at Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2024 to the broader telecom industrial community.

GW: Presented the INSTINCT project as one of its forward-looking activities at its booth at Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2024 and 2025 to the broader telecom industrial community. A demo has been shown in MWC2024. Also, GW presented its RIS solutions, developed in INSTINCT at EuMW2024 in Paris.

NEC: Project-related outcomes have been published in top-tier journals and promoted through posts on the INSTINCT LinkedIn channel. Additionally, NEC has actively participated in workshops, tutorials, and panels at key conferences and events. Notable examples include the IEEE ComSoc 2024 Workshop Series, a tutorial on ISAC at IEEE ICC 2024, and a panel at WCNC 2025, each providing valuable opportunities to share and disseminate the project's activities and findings.

INRIA: Inria's main communication activities thus far concern social media and, specifically LinkedIn, where we have shared content on publications, research stays or other events through the official project LinkedIn page as well as individual pages. Inria will continue to communicate on an institutional level (Inria website, social media – LinkedIn, internal newsletters), thanks to the further development of the Institute's localized LinkedIn pages. Inria hopes also to further highlight CortexLab and its use in the INSTINCT project as well as others to a larger audience using the institutional channels listed above.

INSA Lyon: coordinates with Inria to ensure communication about the project reaches a larger audience through social media (LinkedIn). Communication activities concerning CortexLab will also be shared.

i2CAT: As the leader of T5.1 on communication and dissemination, i2CAT actively monitors all project activities and achievements, strategically reporting them through the LinkedIn social

media channel. To maintain visibility, i2CAT regularly creates and publishes engaging posts covering milestones, partner contributions, research insights, and event participation through a consistent schedule. i2CAT has also monitored engagement, responded to interactions to foster the network, and attended SNS communication task force meetings to align LinkedIn efforts with the broader project messaging and identify collaboration opportunities. Furthermore, i2CAT ensures the accuracy of shared information by staying informed about project developments and proactively keeps all partners updated on SNS news and events. Looking ahead, i2CAT plans to continue proactive and timely communication through a content calendar aligned with upcoming project milestones and deliverables. i2CAT's commitment remains to ensuring communication efforts effectively convey the value and impact of the project to a broad audience

UOulu: UOulu participates in the meetings of two ETSI Industrial Specification Group (ISG) where ISAC related issues are discussed, namely the ISAC ISG and the RIS ISG.

CS-UPS: CS has given presentations at several events, including industrial panels, young professional events, and women in engineering workshops to communicate the finding of the project to a broad audience. Also, CS has contributed to podcasts, such as <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kjb-4UrloPk> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K6t4wv5A4IA>, tailored to the public at large.

TID/TSA: TID and TSA actively promoted its participation in the INSTINCT project through a dedicated blog post on the company's official innovation hub webpage: <https://hub.telefonica.com/investigacion/proyecto-instinct>. This website attracts thousands of readers every month, exposing the project among a diverse and tech-savvy audience. In addition, the announcement was shared via a LinkedIn post on TID's official corporate account, which has over 12,000 followers: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/telefonica-innovacion-digital-distrito-telef%C3%B3nica-hub-de-innovaci%C3%B3n-y-talento-activity-7266050362015391744-38cm?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABiz02ABGj86ld0fxu_1E17ceW331rhGcCw. These activities amplified the awareness and engagement within the professional community, including potential partners, researchers, and industry stakeholders.

4 Standardisation Report

As part of INSTINCT's commitment to shaping the future of communication technologies, the project has been actively contributing to several standardisation efforts, both at European and international levels. Table 6 lists the participations in technical groups within ETSI's ISG RIS and ISG ISAC, as well as substantial contributions to multiple working groups of 3GPP (SA1, RAN, RAN2).

#	Standardisation activities	Short description of the activities and the reference to the relevant group	Types of standardisation bodies involved	Standardisation bodies involved	Standard references
	1) Revision of an existing standard 2) Elaboration of a new standard 3) Participation in a technical committee 4) Participation in a technical group 5) Elaboration of a workshop agreement 6) Other		1) International 2) European 3) National 4) Other		
1	3	ISG RIS - Participation in a technical group and related discussions: Industry Specification Group (ISG) Reflective Intelligent Surfaces (RIS)	2	ETSI	
2	3	ISG ISAC - Participation in a technical group and related discussions: Industry Specification Group (ISG) Integrated Sensing And Communications (ISAC)	2	ETSI	
3	2,3,4,5	In SA1 WG, Bosch is active in ICAS where two documents were presented on the following topics. 1. Study on 6G Use Cases and Service Requirements" in multiple topics. 2. Subnetworks, and its use cases, characteristics, difference to	1	3GPP	1. Tdoc S1-242082 "Bosch's view on 6G areas of interest". 2. Tdoc S1-241194 : Vertical's view on 6G: 3GPP Subnetworks

		existing 3GPP communication modes/solutions			3.TDoc on Integrated Sensing and Communications (RWS-230469)
4	2,3,4,5	In RAN plenary workgroup, Bosch presented general Consideration on 5G-Advanced Evolution from the Vertical Markets. In addition, Bosch presented its proposal on the impact of IMT-2030 study on RAN.	1	3GPP	RP-243081: Views on RAN Study Item for IMT-2030 RP-243110: Considerations on 5G-Advanced Evolution from Vertical
5	2,3,4,5	In RAN2 work group , Bosch handles the following <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observation and contribution to ambient IoT study item in RAN2 • Observation of random access procedure and functionality aspects of ambient IoT 	1	3GPP	R2-2408671: Discussions on Energy Status Report in Ambient IoT Devices R2-2408672: Discussions on Failure Detection/Recovery in Ambient IoT Devices
6	2,3,4,5	WI 076 - Open RAN for Industrial 5G	1	5G-ACIA	WI076's internal report on "Open RAN for Industrial 5G"
7	6(Observation)	WI-083 Use Cases and Requirements for Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) in Connected Industries and Automation	1	5G-ACIA	
8	6(Observation)	WI 087 Early considerations of network capability evolution for industries and automation	1	5G-ACIA	
9	6(Observation)	Work Item on ISAC	1	5GAA	
10	2	Concepts on beam focusing, near field communications and wavefront engineering developed in INSTINCT have been contributed and included in new Report ITU-R M.2541 on the	1	ITU-R WP5D	Report ITU-R M.2541 on the "Technical feasibility of IMT in

		“Technical feasibility of IMT in bands above 100 GHz”.			bands above 100 GHz”.
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Table 6: Standardisation efforts

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable, we reported the dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities performed during the first 18 months of the INSTINCT project. In the dissemination activities, we listed a total of 51 journal publications, 25 conference publications, 3 book chapters and 30 talks and other related events. These numbers support the strong commitment of INSTINCT to work towards spreading the project results to a wide audience. Among the different dissemination activities, INSTINCT had presence at EUCNC 2025 where they showcased two out of the three demonstrators, offering a tangible look at the work done within the project.

Related to the communication activities, we have seen a huge interest from the audience in the INSTINCT project which was reflected in the large incoming/outcoming traffic to the website. In addition, the LinkedIn account is being successful and is receiving a lot of attention thanks to the strategy we adopted at the inception of the project. So far, we have gathered 470 subscriptions, more than 45000 impressions and more than 800 reactions. A quarterly newsletter was published with a general overview on the project, the descriptions of the work packages and a list of key events and publications done within the scope of INSTINCT. Finally, a total of 10 standardisation activities have been performed involving different standardisation bodies such as 3GPP and ETSI.